

ANATOMICAL AND COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY STUDY OF THE MANDIBLE OF BROWN BEARS (*URSUS ARCTOS*)

Iliana Ruzhanova-Gospodinova¹, Seven Mustafa², Silvi Vladova³, Buket Çakar⁴,
Burak Ünal⁵, Barış Can Güzel⁶

¹*Department of Anatomy, Physiology and Animal Sciences, University of Forestry,
1797 Sofia, Bulgaria*

²*Department of Surgery, Radiology, Obstetrics and Gynecology, University of Forestry,
1797 Sofia, Bulgaria*

³*Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Forestry, 1797 Sofia, Bulgaria*

⁴*Institute of Graduate Studies, Istanbul University-Cerrahpasa, 34320 Istanbul, Türkiye*

⁵*Department of Anatomy, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Istanbul University-Cerrahpasa, 34320
Istanbul, Türkiye*

⁶*Department of Anatomy, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Siirt University, 56100 Siirt, Türkiye
E-mail: iliana_ruzhanova@ltu.bg*

ORCID: 0000-0002-5855-9996 I.R.G.; 0000-0002-5895-5796 S.M.; 0009-0009-4076-7568 B.Ç.;
0009-0002-9806-2519 B.Ü.; 0000-0002-2504-120X B.C.G.

(Submitted: 23 October 2025; Accepted: 15 January 2026; Published: 30 March 2026)

ABSTRACT

Understanding mandibular anatomy in brown bears (*Ursus arctos*) is essential for interpreting their feeding ecology and adaptive strategies. This study aims to provide a detailed morphological and morphometric analysis of the brown bear mandible using advanced imaging techniques, and to investigate how these anatomical features relate to the species' omnivorous dietary habits. Twelve adult mandibles were obtained from brown bears that died of natural causes or were culled as part of wildlife population management programs. All specimens were scanned using high-resolution computed tomography. The computed tomography datasets were processed using specialized segmentation software to generate accurate three-dimensional reconstructions of the mandibles. These digital models were then subjected to both morphometric measurements and qualitative anatomical assessment. The analysis revealed mandibular characteristics well-adapted to omnivorous feeding, including a robust coronoid process, a broad pterygoid fossa, a strong mandibular condyle, and a well-defined mandibular canal, all of which contribute to efficient mastication of both animal and plant materials. Although the sample size was limited to 12 specimens, which may constrain the generalizability of the findings, the use of non-destructive, high-resolution imaging techniques allowed for precise anatomical characterization. The results provide important insights into the species' functional morphology and have potential applications in both comparative anatomy and clinical veterinary practice. This study establishes a baseline for future comparative investigations into mandibular form and function in omnivorous mammals.

Key words: functional morphology, morphometry, mandibular canal, 3D reconstruction, feeding biomechanics, wildlife veterinary anatomy.

Introduction

The family Ursidae belongs to the order Carnivora and comprises large, powerful terrestrial mammals. Originating and evolving in the Northern Hemisphere, members of this family are currently distributed across Eurasia, North Africa, and North America. Although the taxonomic diversity within Ursidae is relatively limited, the eight extant species display remarkable ecological and

behavioral adaptations that have enabled them to inhabit diverse environments ranging from tropical rainforests to Arctic ice sheets (Herrero *et al.*, 1999).

Living bears today are distinctly differentiated from other carnivores by their large body sizes (Gittleman, 1985), characterized by large skulls with reduced premolars in both the upper and lower jaws and well-developed molars. These morphological traits generally correspond to their feeding behaviors, especially in the mandible (Van Heteren *et al.*, 2009; Van Heteren *et al.*, 2016). For instance, carnivorous bears such as the polar bear (*Ursus maritimus*) possess smaller carnassial teeth and enhanced bite forces suitable for capturing and processing large prey (Sacco and Van Valkenburgh, 2004). In contrast, herbivorous bears like the extinct cave bear (*Ursus spelaeus*) exhibit larger molars and more robust mandibles adapted for processing fibrous plant materials (Figueirido *et al.*, 2009; Figueirido & Van Heteren, 2019). Additionally, insectivorous bears such as the sloth bear (*Melursus ursinus*) show a smaller mandibular ramus and a more curved mandible, while both carnivorous and herbivorous bears share wide diastemas and mandibles of similar length anteriorly and posteriorly (Meloro, 2011). Omnivorous bears, including the brown bear (*Ursus arctos*), display intermediate mandibular morphologies reflecting their generalized diet (Van Heteren *et al.*, 2009; Van Heteren *et al.*, 2014). These morphological distinctions reflect ecological adaptations and provide a framework for detailed taxonomic and functional analyses within Ursidae.

Medical imaging techniques enable the acquisition of two-dimensional (2D) images of anatomical structures; however, 2D imaging is limited by factors such as magnification errors, superimposition, and lack of depth perception. These limitations have driven the increasing use of three-dimensional (3D) imaging methods, whereby 2D sectional images can be reconstructed into 3D models using specialized software (Akbas *et al.*, 2023; Gundemir *et al.*, 2021, 2023a; Senol *et al.*, 2022). Such 3D reconstructions allow precise visualization, measurement, and segmentation of anatomical structures (Demircioğlu *et al.*, 2021; Özkadif & Eken, 2015; De Freitas *et al.*, 2011; Sergovich *et al.*, 2010). The advancement of these technologies has facilitated their application in zooarchaeology, morphometrics, and biomechanical modeling studies, enabling detailed anatomical and functional analyses (Lloyd *et al.*, 2018; Evin *et al.*, 2016; Djorojevic, 2014;).

In this study, we aim to construct a high-resolution 3D model of the mandible of the brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) and perform a detailed morphological analysis. These morphological data will be compared with those of other bear species, including the polar bear (*Ursus maritimus*) and the extinct cave bear (*Ursus spelaeus*), to identify species-specific similarities and differences. Furthermore, we will investigate the 3D anatomical features of the brown bear's mandibular canal and analyze the sectional morphology of its teeth to provide comprehensive data on the jaw's structural and functional attributes related to feeding biomechanics. Our hypothesis is that the brown bear's mandibular morphology reflects its omnivorous diet and ecological versatility, and that distinct anatomical features will correspond to its evolutionary adaptations. The findings are expected to advance understanding of bear ecomorphology and contribute valuable insights to comparative anatomy and conservation efforts.

Materials and Methods

This study examined the skulls of 12 deceased brown bears (*Ursus arctos*) from the Bear Sanctuary Belitsa in Bulgaria, affiliated with the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine at the University of Forestry. Age and approximate weight information were obtained from the park's records for all but one specimen. Detailed information about the samples is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Samples used in the study, their sex, age, and estimated weight.

Samples	Sex	Age	Weight (kg, Approximately)
1	Female	39	100
2	Male	34	250
3	Female	30	150
4	Male	29	300
5	Male	32	200
6	Male	31	300
7	Female	37	120
8	Male	33	206
9	Male	36	200
10	Female	37	100
11	Female	34	100
12	Male	Unknown	Unknown

Computer Tomography information

The computed tomography study was performed on Siemens Somatom go. Now CT scanner (Siemens Healthineers, Germany), using the factory Brain Multi Phase protocol with slice thickness of 0.5 mm and syngo CT VA40A software version.

Segmentation

Mandibular samples from 12 brown bears were acquired in DICOM format. The DICOM datasets were imported into 3D Slicer (open-source software for medical image computing, version 4.11 or later) for three-dimensional reconstruction and analysis.” Segmentation of the mandible was performed using the thresholding function, with threshold values set between 230.38 and 5372.09, allowing the generation of accurate three-dimensional mandibular models.

The mandibular canal was segmented semi-automatically using a combination of thresholding and region-growing tools, followed by manual refinement to ensure anatomical accuracy.

The volume and surface area of the mandibular canal were calculated using the Segment Statistics module of 3D Slicer.

Measurement points

Linear morphometric measurements of the mandible were performed following previously established protocols for mandibular morphometry (Núñez-Cook *et al.*, 2024; Jashari *et al.*, 2022; Ozkan *et al.*, 2020). Measurements were taken between predefined anatomical landmarks distributed across the mandibular body and ramus (Fig. 1).

The following parameters were recorded: total mandibular length and height, body length, ramus length, diastema length, tooth row length, molar and premolar row lengths, condylar height, incisura height, and distances between the mandibular and mental foramina and adjacent anatomical landmarks (Table 2).

Morphometric assessment of the mandibular canal included cross-sectional measurements of its maximum and minimum diameters, as well as the maximum and minimum diameters of the

mandibular and mental foramina, following established morphometric approaches (Jashari *et al.*, 2022; Ozkan *et al.*, 2020). Canal volume and surface area were also calculated (Fig. 2, Table 3).

Static analysis

Statistical analysis of the data was performed using SPSS (version 27.0) software. Following normality testing, an independent samples t-test was applied to assess sexual dimorphism in normally distributed data. Mandibular measurements were presented as mean \pm standard error (SE).

Figure 1: Linear Measurement Points of the Mandible in the Brown Bear

Figure 2: Brown Bear Mandibular Canal (Canalis Mandibularis) Visualization (A: Medial Surface; B: Lateral Surface; Yellow: Canalis Mandibularis)

Results

The mandible of brown bears consists of two parts connected by the symphysis (articulatio intermandibularis). The mandible is characterized by a distinct corpus mandibulae, ramus mandibulae, and angulus mandibulae, all adapted to the bear's strong chewing capability and dietary habits. Detailed measurements results are given in Table 2.

Medial surface of the mandible

The medial surface of the mandible is generally smooth, featuring the *foramen mandibulae* located caudomedially. This foramen marks the entry point of the mandibular nerve and vessels

into the mandibular canal. Just ventral to this foramen, a shallow groove called the *sulcus mylohyoideus* can be observed, which serves as the attachment site for the *m. mylohyoideus* and is more pronounced in females.

Ramus and angulus regions of the mandible

The *ramus mandibulae* is a robust structure for the attachment of jaw muscles and a deep depression, the *fossa masseterica*, is present in this region to anchor the *m. masseter*. The *angulus mandibulae* forms a distinct angle between the body and the ramus, optimizing the distribution of chewing forces. The prominent *processus angularis* extends from the *angulus mandibulae*, providing additional support and stability for the mandible and enhancing the efficiency of jaw muscle attachments.

Proc. condylaris and proc. coronoideus

The *proc. condylaris*, part of the jaw joint, is larger and more prominent in males, while it is broader and flatter in females. This difference reflects the variation in jaw muscle size between genders. In males, the *processus angularis* forms a more superficial notch, whereas in females, the notch is shallower.

The *proc. coronoideus* is a critical attachment point for chewing muscles. This structure is perpendicular to the horizontal plane, with its upper edge oriented ventro-dorsally, enabling effective muscle attachment and movement.

Functional and morphological features

The mandible of the brown bear stands out with its strong jaw muscles, large teeth, and functional anatomy. The size and number of premolars and molars make it well-suited for grinding animal and plant materials. The oversized canine teeth are adapted for hunting and defense, while the wide diastema facilitates efficient jaw movements. Structural differences between males and females highlight the species' ecological and sexual dimorphism.

Canalis mandibulae

The *canalis mandibulae* originates at the mandibular foramen on the medial surface of the *ramus mandibulae* and extends through the mandibular body. The canal is divided into three main segments: the caudal segment, the intermediate segment, and the rostral segment.

The caudal segment extends from the mandibular foramen to the caudal part of the last molar tooth. At its beginning, this segment descends into the depth of the medial surface of the ramus, then progresses along the mandible, terminating near the roots of the molar teeth.

The intermediate segment lies between the caudal part of the last molar and the first premolar, extending between the last molar and the first premolar tooth. This segment contains small foramina near the roots of the teeth, which become progressively more minor as the canal advances.

The rostral segment starts at the rostral margin of the first premolar and ends at the mental foramen. As the canal progresses towards the anterior part of the mandible, it eventually turns laterally and runs horizontally. The final part of the rostral segment widens laterally as it reaches the mental foramen, where it branches into alveolar canals extending towards the incisors.

The morphometric measurements of the mandibular canal, including its volume and surface area, are detailed in Table 3. These data provide insights into the length, diameter, and relationships between each segment and surrounding anatomical structures, aiding in a more comprehensive understanding of the canal's spatial configuration.

Table 2: Detailed linear measurements of the brown bear mandibles: CH, condyle height; FMC, distance between the caudal margin of the mandible and the mandibular foramen; FmC, distance between the rostral margin of the first premolar and the mental foramen; FMO, distance between the angle of the mandible and the mandibular foramen; FmR, distance between the mental foramen and the first incisor; FMV, distance between the ventral margin of the angle and the mandibular foramen; FmV, distance between the ventral margin of the mandible and the mental foramen; HCM3, body height caudal to the third molar; HRP1, body height rostral to the first premolar; HRM1 - body height rostral to the first molar; IH, incisura height; LAFm, length between the angle and the mental foramen; LAP, length between the angle and the first premolar; LB, body length; LFA, mandibular length from the angle to the first incisor alveolus; LFC, mandibular length from the condyle to the first incisor alveolus; LMR, molar row length; LPR, premolar row length; LR, ramus length; LTR, tooth row length; TML, total mandibular length; TMH, total mandibular height.

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Error Mean	P
TMH	Male	7	99.54	0.73	NS
	Female	5	83.41	1.71	
TML	Male	7	249.91	4.01	NS
	Female	5	209.00	3.26	
LFA	Male	7	244.88	3.91	NS
	Female	5	207.88	3.88	
LFC	Male	7	248.18	3.91	*
	Female	5	171.40	37.56	
LR	Male	7	80.34	5.20	NS
	Female	5	68.09	3.04	
LB	Male	7	161.25	2.91	NS
	Female	5	139.38	2.28	
LAP	Male	7	218.15	13.73	NS
	Female	5	179.92	7.43	
LAFm	Male	7	166.15	5.02	*
	Female	5	150.42	2.86	
LTR	Male	7	127.90	3.66	NS
	Female	5	110.28	6.19	
LMR	Male	7	69.40	2.18	NS
	Female	5	59.78	2.68	
LPR	Male	7	57.13	3.49	NS
	Female	5	49.68	5.23	
CH	Male	7	40.72	2.51	NS
	Female	5	34.28	3.63	
IH	Male	7	43.14	2.57	NS
	Female	5	34.16	1.50	
FMC	Male	7	51.32	2.89	NS
	Female	5	31.65	3.44	
FMV	Male	7	26.36	0.80	NS
	Female	5	22.14	1.63	
FMO	Male	7	56.24	2.01	NS
	Female	5	45.14	1.36	
FmR	Male	7	69.47	4.62	NS
	Female	5	51.08	2.48	
FmV	Male	7	22.61	1.97	NS
	Female	5	19.98	1.91	
FmC	Male	7	32.68	3.72	NS
	Female	5	25.70	5.65	
HRP1	Male	7	46.45	3.16	NS
	Female	5	37.62	2.38	
HRM1	Male	7	52.61	2.83	NS
	Female	5	39.40	2.35	
HCM3	Male	7	56.62	1.68	NS
	Female	5	45.89	1.84	

Table 3: Detailed linear measurements (mean \pm SE; cm), volume (mm³), and surface area (mm²) of the mandibular canal of brown bears: MDC, maximum diameter of the mandibular canal in cross-sectional view (measured

according to canal height); mDC, minimum diameter of the mandibular canal in cross-sectional view (measured according to canal height); MDMF, maximum diameter of the mandibular foramen; mDMF, minimum diameter of the mandibular foramen; MDmF, maximum diameter of the mental foramen; mDmF, minimum diameter of the mental foramen.

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Error Mean	P
MDC	1.00	7	19.13	3.64	NS
	2.00	5	13.55	5.72	
mDC	1.00	7	10.08	2.66	NS
	2.00	5	7.96	1.17	
MDMF	1.00	7	17.72	2.52	NS
	2.00	5	14.40	4.29	
mDMF	1.00	7	12.53	1.30	NS
	2.00	5	8.32	1.06	
MDmF	1.00	7	10.21	1.54	NS
	2.00	5	7.93	1.63	
mDmF	1.00	7	7.60	1.99	NS
	2.00	5	6.82	1.63	
Surface(mm ²)	1.00	7	7946.70	1270.99	NS
	2.00	5	8198.29	1191.09	
Volume(mm ³)	1.00	7	10021.72	1651.35	NS
	2.00	5	7523.50	3750.30	

Discussion

This study provides novel anatomical data on the mandible of brown bears (*Ursus arctos*), based on detailed morphometric measurements and advanced imaging of twelve specimens. The results highlight specific morphological variations linked to sexual dimorphism and size differences, which contribute directly to understanding the species' feeding mechanics and ecological adaptations (Ruzhanova-Gospodinova *et al.*, 2024).

Using advanced imaging techniques, our comprehensive evaluation revealed significant size differences between males and females, with males exhibiting larger mandibular dimensions across 63 measured variables. This quantification of sexual dimorphism in mandibular morphology reflects important biological and ecological implications related to feeding efficiency and prey selection within the species (Loy *et al.*, 2008). Furthermore, the 3D modeling of the mandibular canal provided detailed anatomical visualization, offering a novel resource that can support future clinical applications, such as the development of targeted regional anesthetic techniques specific to brown bears (Cotrim *et al.*, 2015; Martinez *et al.*, 2010).

Sexual dimorphism, well-documented in vertebrates (Derocher *et al.*, 2005), was directly assessed and quantified in this study. Our findings confirm that size disparities between males and females are significantly reflected in mandibular morphology, consistent with their ecological roles and behavioral strategies. For example, the sulcus mylohyoideus – a groove for muscle attachment—was notably more prominent in females, suggesting functional differences in muscle attachment sites that may influence feeding mechanics (Figueirido *et al.*, 2009; Figueirido & Van Heteren, 2019). These results offer new empirical evidence linking morphological features to ecological function, advancing beyond prior descriptive accounts.

The mandibular morphological differences observed align with species-specific feeding behaviors and habitat utilization patterns (Van Heteren *et al.*, 2016; Reid *et al.*, 1991). While previous studies suggested dietary variations among bear species, our morphometric data provide precise confirmation that brown bears possess mandibular characteristics adapted for an omnivorous diet.

This is exemplified by subspecies-specific variations in diastema width and mandibular robustness (Ciucci *et al.*, 2014; Aryal *et al.*, 2012), illustrating adaptive morphological plasticity shaped by environmental and dietary pressures.

From a clinical perspective, our study presents the first detailed osteometric data on mandibular and mental foramina locations in brown bears, which are critical landmarks for effective regional anesthesia during veterinary interventions (Beckman and Legendre, 2002; Kierdorf *et al.*, 2016; Paulo *et al.*, 2020). The mandibular foramen was consistently positioned 2.5–2.7 cm from the ventral edge and 4–6 cm from the caudal border of the mandible, whereas the mental foramen was located 3–4 cm caudoventral to the anterior mandible and approximately 1–2 cm below the canine tooth. These precise measurements serve as essential reference points for minimally invasive clinical procedures in wild brown bears, filling a notable gap in the anatomical literature.

Our 3D visualization and modeling of the mandibular canal also clarified its structural features, confirming that it is not a medullary canal (Cotrim *et al.*, 2015). This insight is vital for surgical planning, as it highlights the risk of neurovascular damage when employing intramedullary fixation techniques for mandibular fractures, underscoring the necessity of species-specific surgical protocols.

In conclusion, this study delivers new, species-specific anatomical data on the brown bear mandible, clarifying morphological variations associated with sex, size, and ecological factors. These findings enhance our understanding of the species' biology and feeding ecology and hold significant implications for veterinary care and conservation strategies (Ruzhanova-Gospodinova *et al.*, 2024). By establishing comprehensive morphometric baselines, this work fills a critical knowledge gap and lays the groundwork for future research in bear morphology, functional biomechanics, and clinical applications.

Acknowledgements

The authors sincerely thank Multidisciplinary Veterinary Clinic Bulgaria and Bear Sanctuary Belitsa, whose support and collaboration have been fundamental to completing this research endeavor.

Conflict of interest

Authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

References

1. Ağaç, D. K., Onuk, B., Gündemir, O., Kabak, M., Manuta, N., Çakar, B., ... & Szara, T. (2024). *Comparative cranial geometric morphometrics among Wistar albino, Sprague Dawley, and WAG/Rij rat strains*. *Animals*, 14(9), 1274.
2. Akbaş, Z. S., Duro, S., Yalin, E. E., Gündemir, O., Özkan, E., & Szara, T. (2023). *Detection of sexual dimorphism of the foramen magnum in cats using computed tomography*. *Anatomia, Histologia, Embryologia*, 52(4), 595–602.
3. Aryal, A., Hopkins, J. B., Raubenheimer, D., Ji, W., & Brunton, D. (2012). *Distribution and diet of brown bears in the upper Mustang Region, Nepal*. *Ursus*, 23(2), 231–236.
4. Audisio, S. A., P. G. Vaquero, P. A. Torres, and E. C. Verna. (2011). *Prevención, manejo y tratamiento del dolor quirúrgico*. 1st ed. Santa Rosa: Universidad Nacional de La Pampa.

5. Beckman, B., and L. Legendre. (2002). *Regional Nerve Blocks for Oral Surgery in Companion Animals*. Compendium on Continuing Education for the Practising Veterinarian 24: 439–444.
6. Christiansen, P. (2007). *Evolutionary implications of bite mechanics and feeding ecology in bears*. Journal of Zoology, 272(4), 423–443.
7. Ciucci, P., Tosoni, E., Di Domenico, G., Quattrociochi, F., & Boitani, L. (2014). *Seasonal and annual variation in the food habits of Apennine brown bears, central Italy*. Journal of Mammalogy, 95(3), 572–586.
8. Clarke, K. W., and C. M. Trim. (2013). *Veterinary Anaesthesia e- Book*. 1st ed. Amsterdam, The Netherlands: Elsevier Health Sciences.
9. Cotrim, S. C., J. R. B. Nardotto, L. G. Abreu, A. R. L. Silva, P. D. Galera, and M. I. S. Santana. (2015). *Estudo anatômico do trajeto do canal mandibular em felinos (Felis catus domesticus)*. Arquivo Brasileiro de Medicina Veterinária e Zootecnia 67: 1581–1588. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1678-4162-8325>.
10. Courtenay, L. A., Maté-González, M. Á., Aramendi, J., Yravedra, J., González-Aguilera, D., & Domínguez-Rodrigo, M. (2018). *Testing accuracy in 2D and 3D geometric morphometric methods for cut mark identification and classification*. Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports, 18, 529–542.
11. De Freitas, E. P., Noritomi, P. Y., & da Silva, J. V. L. (2011). *Use of rapid prototyping and 3D reconstruction in veterinary medicine*. In Advanced applications of rapid prototyping Technology in Modern Engineering. IntechOpen.
12. Demircioglu, I., Yilmaz, B., Gündemir, O., & Dayan, M. O. (2021). *A three-dimensional pelvimetric assessment on pelvic cavity of gazelle (Gazella subgutturosa) by computed tomography*. Anatomia, Histologia, Embryologia, 50(1), 43–49.
13. Derocher, A. E., & Stirling, I. (1998). *Geographic variation in growth of polar bears (Ursus maritimus)*. Journal of Zoology, 245(1), 65–72.
14. Djorojevic, M., Roldán, C., García-Parra, P., Alemán, I. & Botella, M. (2014). *Morphometric sex estimation from 3D computed tomography os coxae model and its validation in skeletal remains*. International journal of legal medicine. 128. 879–888.
15. Evin, A., Souter, T., Hulme-Beaman, A., Ameen, C., Allen, R., Viacava, P. & Dobney, K. (2016). *The use of close-range photogrammetry in zooarchaeology: Creating accurate 3D models of wolf crania to study dog domestication*. Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports. 9. 87–93.
16. Figueirido, B., & van Heteren, A. H. (2019). *The story continues: recent advances on the life and death of the Pleistocene cave bear*. Historical Biology, 31(4), 405–409.
17. Figueirido, B., Palmqvist, P., & Pérez-Claros, J. A. (2009). *Ecomorphological correlates of craniodental variation in bears and paleobiological implications for extinct taxa: an approach based on geometric morphometrics*. Journal of Zoology, 277(1), 70–80.
18. Gittleman, J. L. (1985). *Carnivore body size: ecological and taxonomic correlates*. Oecologia. 67. 540–554.
19. Glatt, S. E., K. E. Francl, and J. L. Scheels. (2008). *A Survey of Current Dental Problems and Treatments of Zoo Animals*. International Zoo Yearbook 42: 206–213. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1748-1090.2007.00032.x>.
20. Gordon, K. R. & Morejohn, G. V. (1975). *Sexing black bear skulls using lower canine and lower molar measurements*. The Journal of Wildlife Management. 40–44.
21. Gündemir, O. (2023b). *Shape analysis of fossa masseterica and processus coronoideus in domestic cats (Felis catus) and domestic dogs (Canis familiaris)*. Anatomia, Histologia, Embryologia, 52(6), 899–906.

22. Gündemir, O., Michaud, M., Altundağ, Y., Karabağlı, M., Onar, V., & Crampton, D. (2024). *Chewing asymmetry in dogs: Exploring the importance of the fossa masseterica and first molar teeth morphology*. *Anatomia, Histologia, Embryologia*, 53(3), e13050.
23. Gündemir, O., Szara, T., Pazvant, G., Erdikmen, D. O., Duro, S., & Perez, W. (2021). *Radiogrametric analysis of the thoracic limb phalanges in Arabian horses and thoroughbred horses*. *Animals*, 11(8), 2205.
24. Gündemir, O., Szara, T., Yalin, E. E., Karabağlı, M., Mutlu, Z., Yilmaz, O., ... & Parés-Casanova, P. M. (2023a). *Examination of shape variation of the skull in British Shorthair, Scottish Fold, and Van Cats*. *Animals*, 13(4), 614.
25. Hall, L. W., K. W. Clarke, and C. M. Trim. (2000). *Wright's Veterinary Anaesthesia and Analgesia*. 10th ed. London: ELBS and Bailliere Tindall.
26. Herrero, S., Peyton, B. & Servheen, C. (1999). *Bears: status survey and conservation action plan*. IUCN/SSC Bear Specialist Group, IUCN, Gland, Switzerland and Cambridge, UK.
27. Hwang, M. H., Garshelis, D. L., & Wang, Y. (2002). *Diets of Asiatic black bears in Taiwan, with methodological and geographical comparisons*. *Ursus*, 111–125.
28. Jashari, T., Duro, S., Gündemir, O., Szara, T., Ilieski, V., Mamuti, D., & Choudhary, O. P. (2022). *Morphology, morphometry and some aspects of clinical anatomy in the skull and mandible of Sharri sheep*. *Biologia*, 77(2), 423–433.
29. Kierdorf, H., O. Filevych, W. Lutz, and U. Kierdorf. (2016). *Dental Defects as a Potential Indicator of Chronic Malnutrition in a Population of Fallow Deer (Dama dama) From Northwestern Germany*. An Kurtén, B., 1955. Sex dimorphism and size trends in the cave bear. *Acta Zoologica Fennica* 90, 1–47.
30. Kurtén, B., 1968. *Pleistocene Mammals of Europe*. Weidenfeld and Nicholson, London. *Atomical Record* (Hoboken, N.J.: 2007) 299, no. 10: 1409–1423. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ar.23459>.
31. Magalhães, H. I. R., F. B. Romão, Y. H. de Paula, et al. (2019). *Morphometry of the Mandibular Foramen Applied to Local Anesthesia in Hoary Fox (Lycalopex vetulus)*. *Pesquisa Veterinaria Brasileira* 39: 278–285. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1678-5150-PVB-5749>.
32. Magalhães, H. I. R., R. L. Ferreira Júnior, Y. H. de Paula, et al. (2019). *Morphometry of Mental Foramina Applied to Local Anesthesia in Hoary Fox (Lycalopex vetulus Lund, 1842)*. *International Journal of Morphology* 37: 1486–1492. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0717-95022019000401486>.
33. Martinez, L. A. V., M. A. Gioso, C. M. V. Lobos, and A. C. B. de Campos Fonseca. (2010). *Determinação do trajeto do canal mandibular por meio de tomografia computadorizada em dez mandíbulas de cadáveres de cães mesaticefálicos*. *Brazilian Journal of Veterinary Research and Animal Science* 47, no. 4: 274–281. <https://doi.org/10.11606/issn.16784456.bjvras.2010.26826>.
34. Mattson, D. J. (1998). *Diet and morphology of extant and recently extinct northern bears*. *Ursus*. 479–496.
35. Meloro, C. (2011). *Feeding habits of Plio-Pleistocene large carnivores as revealed by the mandibular geometry*. *Journal of vertebrate Paleontology*. 31(2). 428–446.
36. Núñez-Cook, S., Vidal, F., & Salinas, P. (2024). *Anatomical and computed tomography study of the mandible of the Patagonian huemul (Hippocamelus bisulcus): Ecological and clinical insights*. *Anatomia, Histologia, Embryologia*, 53(6), e13108.
37. Ozkadif, S. & Eken, E. (2015). *Contribution of virtual anatomic models to medical education*. *Atatürk Üniversitesi Veteriner Bilimleri Dergisi*. 10(1).
38. Ozkan, E., Jashari, T., Gündemir, O., & Gezer İnce, N. (2020). *Morphometric analysis of the mandible of Bardhoka autochthonous sheep in Kosovo*. *Anatomia, histologia, embryologia*, 49(6), 737–741.

39. Paulo, C. B., H. I. R. Magalhães, Y. H. de Paula, et al. (2020). *Morphometry of the Mandibular Foramen Applied to the Local Anesthetic Block to Inferior Alveolar Nerve in Boars (Sus scrofa scrofa Linnaeus, 1758)*. Brazilian Journal of Veterinary Research and Animal Science 57: e161658.
40. Reid, D., Jiang, M., Teng, Q., Qin, Z., & Hu, J. (1991). *Ecology of the Asiatic black bear (Ursus thibetanus) in Sichuan, China*.
41. Ruzhanova-Gospodinova, I. S., Vladova, S., Szara, T., Tandir, F., Szara, E., Yalin, E. E., & Gündemir, O. (2024). *Morpho-Geometric Description of the Skulls and Mandibles of Brown Bears (Ursus arctos) from the Dancing Bear Belitsa Park*. Animals: an Open Access Journal from MDPI, 14(17), 2541.
42. Sacco, T. & Van Valkenburgh, B. (2004). *Ecomorphological indicators of feeding behaviour in the bears (Carnivora: Ursidae)*. Journal of Zoology. 263(1). 41–54.
43. Senol, E., Gündemir, O., Duro, S., Szara, T., Demiraslan, Y., & Karadağ, H. (2022). *A pilot study: Can calcaneus radiographic image be used to determine sex and breed in cats?* Veterinary Medicine and Science, 8(5), 1855–1861.
44. Sergovich A., Johnson M., Wilson TD. (2010). *Explorable three-dimensional digital model of the female pelvis. pelvis contents. and perineum for anatomical education*. Anatomical Sciences Education. 3. 127–133
45. Slater, G. J., Figueirido, B., Louis, L., Yang, P., & Van Valkenburgh, B. (2010). *Biomechanical consequences of rapid evolution in the polar bear lineage*. PLoS One, 5(11), e13870.
46. Stirling, I. & Archibald, W. R. (1977). *Aspects of predation of seals by polar bears*. Journal of the Fisheries Board of Canada, 34(8), 1126-1129.
47. Van Heteren, A. H., MacLarnon, A., Soligo, C. & Rae, T. C. (2014). *Functional morphology of the cave bear (Ursus spelaeus) cranium: a three-dimensional geometric morphometric analysis*. Quaternary International. 339. 209–216.
48. Van Heteren, A. H., MacLarnon, A. Soligo, C. & Rae, T. C. (2016). *Functional morphology of the cave bear (Ursus spelaeus) mandible: a 3D geometric morphometric analysis*. Organisms Diversity & Evolution. 16. 299–314.
49. Van Heteren, A., MacLarnon, A., Rae, T. & Soligo, C. (2009). *Cave bears and their closest living relatives: a 3D geometric morphometrical approach to the functional morphology of the cave bear Ursus spelaeus*. Acta Carsologica Slovaca. 47(S1). 33–46.
50. Wang, X., A. Liu, J. Zhao, F. M. Elshaer, and D. Massoud. (2021). *Anatomy of the Skull of Saanen Goat. An Anesthesiology and Stereology Approach*. International Journal of Morphology 39, No. 2: 423–429.